

Proof of Existence of Square-free Numbers in Infinity

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ABSTRACT

We give the fool proof by using series and standard O-notation of the existence of square-free numbers in infinity.

Keywords: infinity, proof, square-free numbers.

INTRODUCTION

The infinity is a long-standing term in mathematics and its historical aspect [1, 2]. Recently, the square-free number definition was proposed [3, 4, 5].

We proof by series that there exist the square-free numbers in infinity or in other words their space is unbounded by any constant.

PROOF BY SERIES

Let's define the following function $p(x)$ - where $p(x)$ is the number of square-free forms up to x . As we know the following holds true for any argument x :

$$p(x) \leq x \wedge p(x) \leq O(\sqrt{x}) \leq \int \sqrt{x} = \frac{2}{3} * x^{\frac{3}{2}}.$$

However, the integration above isn't closed and converges to infinity, thus proving that the number square-free naturals is unbound and exists in infinity.

CONCLUSION

We have shown the proof of the existence of square-free numbers in infinity.

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